

THE VALUE OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH DURING
THE PERIOD OF UZBEKISTAN

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An important direction of personality education is ideological education. This is the process of purposeful formation of philosophical, political, legal, religious, aesthetic, moral, artistic, and professional views on life in the system of human consciousness and concepts. Any educational process is ultimately ideological education according to its purpose and essence. Therefore, there cannot be a person without an ideology, a group, a nation, a people, or a society without an ideology.

The goal of ideological education is to raise the educational level of every member of society and every social stratum, and group in their person.

Ideological education is manifested first of all in virtues such as high faith, faith, responsibility to the Motherland and the people, patriotism, dedication, and nationalism.

The new outlook formed in the years of independence implies loyalty to the Motherland, love for national values and traditions, kindness to one's loved ones, loyalty to the chosen path, profession, profession, and faith in young people.

The neighborhood institution has a special place in the formation of a sense of patriotism in young people. A neighborhood is primarily a healthy social environment. Public opinion has a strong influence here, and it regulates the behavior and mutual relations of the community based on moral criteria. In this sense, the influence of the neighborhood on ideological education is strong.

A woman, a mother is a symbol of goodness - a mother has a special place and influence in ideological education. Because the child spends more time with

the mother and receives educational lessons from the parents. Traditions, traditions, customs, customs, ceremonies and holidays passed down from generation to generation as a priceless heritage formed over the centuries serve as an important factor in instilling the main ideas of the national ideology in the young generation.

In the process of ideological education carried out in all educational institutions, in all educational manuals and textbooks, additional literature, the following factors should be given priority:

- Forming a sense of homeland:
- Instilling a love for our mother tongue
- Strengthening respect for national values
- Glorification of a woman who is the epitome of virtue
- Showing the role of the family in raising a sense of patriotism
- To explain that the neighborhood is a classroom of democracy and a school of self-management

- Homeland (Arabic - motherland) is the place where people live, where their descendants and ancestors were born and raised, where the nation was formed, social environment, and country.

The national idea: a dictionary of propaganda technologies and Terms. "Academy" publishing house. - Tashkent 2007. 107 pages.

There are also concepts such as patriotism, development of the country, patriotism, and patriotism related to the concept of homeland.

Patriotism - loyalty to the Motherland, serving it, preserving the country's peace, and encouraging one to be active in the development of the Motherland. Its meaning is to be loving and loyal to the Motherland, to be proud of the country's past and present, and to protect the country's interests. Patriotism means loving the land inherited from ancestors, preserving and developing national traditions and values, protecting one's motherland from enemies, and foreign ideas, and not sparing one's life for its freedom and independence.

2. Ibid., pp. 108,109.

The development of the country depends primarily on the maturity of its children. This encourages each of our compatriots to feel a high responsibility for their spiritual maturity and to live in harmony with the interests of this country and this nation.

This is reflected in the feeling of patriotism.

Patriotism is a concept used to characterize treasonous behavior toward the Motherland. Among such actions, the following can be included: Betraying the interests of the country, engaging in economic, political, and other espionage activities for the sake of one's interests, going over to the enemy's side, and fighting against one's people, country, etc. to engage in dirty work and so on.

Ibid pp. 110-111.

Urgency of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism in the period of the rise of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT.

The article covers the important aspects of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism in the period of the rise of Uzbekistan. It focuses on elucidating the essence of the concepts of homeland, patriotism, patriotism, patriotism, and ideological education. Only the role of patriotic young people in the service of our motherland, our holy homeland has been noted.

In the next three years, the place and status of Uzbekistan in the world community are increasing. It is emphasized in the proverb that its further rise is directly related to the deepening of the worldview of our youth, the increase of intellectual levels, and the health of the sense of patriotism. In addition to this, the wise and fair policy implemented by the head of state and our government is directly related to the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism.

Watangado is a concept applied to people who are forced to leave their homeland due to various socio-economic and political reasons. For example, Furqat Chor, the son of the famous Uzbek democratic and enlightened poet

Zakirjon Kholmuhammad, was forced to leave his country and live in the city of Yorkent as a wandering patriot due to the political pressure of the colonialists of Russia...

Homeland is the past, present, and future of its people. Homeland is a sacred value. Development starts from the motherland. It is the place where the umbilical cord blood of a person is shed, the destination that protects a person from social orphanhood, the spiritual maturity and civil field, the school of life, the school of life, the center of prosperity and happiness.

Homeland is the only one for a person. The country is not big or small, rich or poor. Homeland is not selected. The country is not our mom. That is why it cannot be sold or bought for money.

The homeland cannot be trusted, nor can it be given a loan. Homeland is sacred and unique for every citizen. After all, only people who believe in their country can truly love their country. As mentioned in the hadiths of our Prophet, "To love the motherland is in faith", "That is, every person who has faith and a pure conscience loves the motherland, protects it from the eyes of enemies, fights for its work and living, and its dignity."

Only those who have a sense of patriotism will feel patriotism. The feeling of love for the country is born naturally in the human heart. That is, as a person realizes his identity, and learns his lineage, the feeling of love for the Motherland takes root and grows in his heart. The deeper this root is, the more boundless the love for the country where one was born and raised.

Patriotism should also mean the following:

- to know one's people, and history well and to be proud of it:
- preservation of ancient monuments, unique buildings, and material and spiritual heritage created by ancestors and presented to generations:
- to appreciate and continue the beautiful and spiritual traditions and customs of our people and ancestors:

- in the name of great compatriots-ancestors, to be proud of their great works and creations, to continue their work, to be their worthy heirs:
- to be proud of belonging to such a wonderful nation and country:
- Remembering the names of the heroes who defended the land of Turon and fought against the enemy until the last blood was left in their veins, the heroes who died in fierce battles
- not to forget the thousands of flowers of our nation who suffered imprisonment and exile and died in the repressions organized against our people and nation in the 20th, 30th, 40th, 50th, and finally 80th years of the last century
- this is living with a high faith in our dear and beautiful homeland, always being loyal to it.

The address of President Shavakat Mirziyev to the Oliy MAJLIS dated January 24, 2020, in the education of our youth in the spirit of patriotism, deserves special attention.⁵ After all, in this application, the things that should be done in the future, including the education, enlightenment, employment, sports, art, and recreation of young people are related to socio-economic protection. valuable instructions, guidelines, and recommendations. In this document, our President's concern for fathers towards the youth was demonstrated. Declaring 2020 as the "Ilm" year of enlightenment and development of digital technology indicates that the attention of the government of our country has increased in this direction.

In particular, in the field of preschool education in 2020, kindergartens and high schools for preparing 6-year-old children for high school will be built based on new projects, old ones will be repaired and reconstructed, the library fund of educational institutions will be renewed, and strengthening of the base, complete renovation of schools and universities with modern computer technologies, familiarization of pupils and students with customs and art, etc.

In a word, based on the address of the President to Oliy Majlis, there is a lot of work to be done in 2020. In the implementation of these tasks, true dedication,

patriotism, perseverance, knowledge, courage, honesty, purity, faith, and high culture are required from all the citizens of our country, as well as from our youth.

To conclude, as mentioned above, young people have an important role in the implementation of the reforms implemented in our country, and in educating our people in the spirit of nationalism and patriotism.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Milliy g'oya: targ'ibot texnologiyalari va atamalar lug'ati “Akademiya” nashiryoti.

- Toshkent 2007 yil, 107 bet.

2. Milliy g'oya: targ'ibot texnologiyalari va atamalar lug'ati “Akademiya” nashiryoti

- Toshkent 2007 yi, 108-109 betlar.

3. Milliy g'oya: targ'igot texnologiyalari va atamalar lug'ati “Akademiya” nashiryoti

- Toshkent 2007 yi, 110 bet.

4. Milliy g'oya: targ'ibot texnologiyalari va atamalar lug'ati “Akademiya” nashiryoti

- Toshkent 2007 yi, 111 bet.

5. O'zbekiston Respubilkasi prezident Shavkat Mirziyoyevning oliy majlisga Murajatnomasi.

- Toshkent- “O'zbekiston” 2020 y.